

Site SPHINX TEMPLE Season GS 79-80

Area N. COLONNADE Square R16 Locus Number (3a)

ASSOCIATED POTTERY

Date	Pail No.	total sherds	sherds saved	Field Dates	Sherd Registration	Comments
8/I/80	1	15-16	ALL	8/I/80	GS/ST/N.C./R16 3a	All small, very worn Frag down to minute flakes

ASSOCIATED OBJECTS

Date	Object No.	Pott. Pail	Photo No.	Description/Identification
8/I/80	3	1		Small Flint Flake point, bulb of percussion, 2 non irregular chert frags included

PHOTOGRAPHS

Date	Photo No.	Time	View	Subject

INTERPRETATION

